

1 **Seismic damage assessment of a crude oil hydrodesulphurisation unit.**

2 **Part I: exposure and modelling**

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5 **Abstract**

6 The assets of a hydrodesulphurisation unit of a crude oil refinery are presented in sufficient
7 detail to create a system-wide model for seismic fragility and risk assessment. The assets
8 include pumps, liquid storage tanks, heat exchangers, equipment-supporting buildings,
9 furnaces, process towers, high-temperature separators, and the piping network. Simplified
10 numerical models were employed for the assets, accounting for salient characteristics,
11 functionality, and interconnectivity thereof. Most importantly, a full 3D model of the piping
12 network is provided, which incorporates a simplified representation of the connected structures
13 to capture the dynamic interaction with the piping, enabling cost-effective assessment;
14 increased flexibility in fittings, i.e., elbows, tees, and nozzles, is also accounted for. The end
15 goal is to address the complexities of a small yet critical part of a modern refinery unit and
16 offer a well-documented basis for conducting seismic damage assessment of a critical energy
17 system, which is presented in the companion paper.

18 **Keywords**

19 Crude oil refinery, hydrodesulphurisation unit, exposure model, piping, process assets

20 **1 Introduction**

21 Crude oil refineries play a pivotal role in modern society, serving as the core facilities for
22 processing crude oil into a multitude of refined products, such as gasoline, diesel, jet fuel, and
23 various other petroleum-based products that power transportation, heating, and industrial
24 processes. A crude oil refinery is a complex infrastructure functioning as an integrated system
25 that relies on the smooth and uninterrupted operation of various interconnected components
26 like liquid storage tanks, pumps, process towers, and pressure vessels. However, refineries are
27 vulnerable to natural-technological (NaTech) accidents that may result in severe consequences,
28 spanning from production interruption to fire or explosions. The impacts can be of such
29 magnitude as to be considered credible threats to human health and life, the environment, and
30 the economy (e.g., [1-7]). In particular, earthquake-induced NaTech events have often led to
31 substantial economic and human losses, despite their comparatively lower frequency of
32 occurrence compared to NaTech events caused by storms, tropical storms, extreme
33 temperatures, lightning, or flooding [7].

34 Accordingly, researchers have developed numerical models for assessing the seismic response
35 of individual industrial structures, such as liquid storage tanks, pipelines, and pressure vessels.
36 The perspectives of these studies vary, with some introducing complex asset-specific and
37 detailed-laden models for pressure vessels (e.g., [8-10]), liquid storage tanks (e.g., [11-12]),
38 piping systems (e.g., [11]), and non-structural components and their supporting structure (e.g.,
39 [13]), while others utilising reduced-order models that trade accuracy for generality and

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40 reduced computational cost for pressure vessels (e.g., [14]), liquid storage tanks (e.g., [15-18]),
41 piping systems (e.g., [19, 20]), high-rise stacks (e.g., [21]), and non-structural components with
42 their equipment-supporting buildings (e.g., [22]). Simplified models for pressure vessels have
43 focused on modelling the response of assets such as spherical shells [14] and steel process
44 towers [21]. For liquid storage tanks, early simplified models represented the tanks by
45 constructing an equivalent system comprising an equivalent impulsive fluid mass and an
46 equivalent convective fluid mass [15, 17]. Later models included the uplifting response, which
47 occurs when the base of a tank partially lifts off the ground and influences the overall seismic
48 behaviour of both anchored and unanchored tanks [16, 18]. Simplified models for piping
49 systems have primarily focused on representing the behaviour of pipe segments, with particular
50 emphasis on elbows, which present an increased flexibility compared to straight piping
51 segments and can be more susceptible to seismically induced damage [19, 20]. High-rise stack
52 simplified models include steel chimneys, reinforced concrete chimneys, and steel flares [21].
53 Modelling of building-type industrial structures include reinforced concrete and steel structures
54 [22]. Non-structural components (i.e., equipment items), such as pumps and heat exchangers,
55 are not explicitly modelled in [22] but included as point masses only in the buildings; their
56 seismic response is evaluated by recording peak component acceleration demands and
57 comparing them to the capacity of each components' anchorage system. In other words, only
58 anchorage failure is captured in this simplified modelling approach.

59 Particularly for crude oil refineries, there is a substantial body of literature on the numerical
60 models and associated fragility of liquid storage tanks (e.g., [16, 18]), piping systems (e.g., [19,
61 20]), equipment-supporting buildings (e.g., [22]), and high-rise stacks [21]. However, the
62 aforementioned studies have mostly focused on individual structures, with fewer attempts
63 made to model assets that belong to the same process unit and are functionally and physically
64 interconnected via piping (e.g., [11, 23]). Herein, we aim to provide a comprehensive model of
65 both individual assets and their interconnections via the piping network, enabling a
66 comprehensive representation of a hydrodesulphurisation unit, which lays in the heart of the
67 refining process. In the companion paper [24], this exposure model is used to demonstrate a
68 hazard-consistent (i.e., representative of the hazard of the site) methodology for developing
69 individual asset fragilities and assessing the seismic damage of such critical crude oil refinery
70 units. Ultimately, the detailed exposure model developed in this study is the first step towards
71 performing a comprehensive and advanced seismic risk assessment of a hydrodesulphurisation
72 unit.

73 **2 Hydrodesulphurisation Unit Exposure Model**

74 The purpose of a hydrodesulphurisation (HDS) unit in a typical crude oil refinery is to generate
75 a product, such as diesel, with a sulphur content below a specified threshold [25], e.g., 10 parts
76 per million (ppm) as per the EU Directive 2009/30/EC [26] on the specification of petrol,
77 diesel, and gasoil. The individual structurally independent assets under consideration in the
78 HDS unit exposure model are listed in Table 1. It should be noted that this is not an extensive
79 list of all industrial assets present in the HDS process, but only a list of those that play a critical
80 role in the process and, therefore, are considered assets at risk in case of an earthquake. The
81 HDS unit is relatively simple, especially in terms of piping relative to other very complex
82 refinery units, and at the same time it includes a number of diverse refinery assets that offer
83 depth to the modelling discussion. Most importantly, damage to the HDS unit is critical not just
84 at the facility but also for the surrounding populated areas due to the high toxicity of the stored
85 and processed products.

Table 1. Structurally independent assets of HDS unit considered in the analysis.

Asset description	Asset ID
Liquid storage tanks	TK-01, TK-02, TK-03, TK-04
Pumps	P-01, P-01S, P-02, P-02S
Heat exchangers	E-01, E-02A, E-02B, E-03A, E-03B
Furnace	H-01
Reactors	R-01, R-02
High-temperature separator	V-01
Stripper	C-01

87

88 The schematic plan of the HDS unit is shown in Figure 1. The raw material processed in the
89 HDS unit is naphtha, which is imported from other upstream refinery units and is stored in two
90 liquid storage tanks (TK-01/02). It is then transported to a series of heat exchangers (E-01, E-
91 02/03A&B), which are nested in an equipment-supporting building; they preheat (i.e., increase
92 the temperature of) the fluid before entering the furnace (H-01). Within the furnace, the fluid
93 undergoes further heating to achieve the requisite processing temperature for the reactors. The
94 hot outlet steam from the furnace is directed to the reactors (R-01/02), where the sulphur
95 content is converted to hydrogen sulphide with the aid of a catalyst. Past the reactors, the fluid
96 passes through two heat exchangers (E-03A&B) for cooling. A high-temperature separator (V-
97 01) then separates the cooled reacted fluid from the hydrogen sulphide. The liquid phase of the
98 desulphurised product is sent to a stripper (C-01), where light fractions are removed with the
99 assistance of steam. Finally, the fluid is transported to a heat exchanger (E-01) for further
100 temperature reduction, before being transported to two liquid storage tanks (TK-03/04). Pumps
101 (P-01/02, P-01S/02S) located within the piping network ensure the circulation of the fluid and
102 its delivery to each unit asset at the necessary pressure.

103 It should be noted that complex industrial systems, such as petrochemical plant units, usually
104 incorporate redundancies to a certain extent. This means that some of the assets can be set off
105 order, e.g., for regular maintenance or unscheduled repairs, with little or no consequence to the
106 production. Also, some assets can operate simultaneously, adopting a partially-in-parallel
107 configuration for increased productivity of the unit. Specifically, each pump in the HDS unit,
108 P-01 and P-02, has a corresponding spare pump, P-01S and P-02S, respectively, that can
109 completely replace the primary pump without consequences to the unit operation. On the other
110 hand, heat exchangers E-02/03A operate partially-in-parallel with E-02/03B, similarly to how
111 reactors R-01 and R-02, and tanks TK-01 with TK-02 function. Taking any of these partially-
112 in-parallel assets offline will reduce productivity, but operations will not cease.

113

114

Figure 1. Schematic plan of the entire HDS unit including the liquid storage tanks.

115 3 Asset Structural Models

116 The assets of the HDS unit are detailed in the subsequent sections, focusing on the mechanical
 117 models developed or adopted for their assessment. For ease-of-use and expediency, simplified
 118 (reduced-order and surrogate) models are employed, which are suitable for a seismic risk
 119 assessment study. They capture only high-level salient characteristics, rather than all details of
 120 the structures, in a mode of application consistent with portfolio-level, rather than structure-
 121 specific assessment. In all cases, models are strictly structural, neglecting any soil-structure
 122 interaction by assuming the presence of firm soil conditions. The OpenSees platform [27] is
 123 employed to model the seismic response of all the assets. As reference, it is recalled that
 124 standards for (typically non-seismic) design, manufacturing, construction, and operation of
 125 industrial assets for crude oil refineries such as pumps, heat exchangers, and pressure vessels
 126 include the ASME Boiler and Pressure Vessel Code (BPVC) Section VIII [28], API 610 [29],
 127 and API 660 [30]. Finally, it is noted that the examined assets are considered to be corrosion-
 128 and defect-free, as well as sufficiently maintained as pre standard industry practice.

129 3.1 Liquid storage tanks

130 Four atmospheric unanchored liquid storage tanks are considered in the HDS unit. The
 131 properties and content of the are listed in Table 2. As discussed in, for example, Bakalis et al.
 132 [18] and Karaferis et al. [31], the fill ratio determines the structural response of liquid storage
 133 tanks. Indeed, the impulsive fluid component of the tank, which is the part of the contained
 134 fluid that moves “rigidly” with the tank walls, and the convective fluid component, which
 135 develops a sloshing motion on the free surface due to earthquake excitation, are closely related
 136 to the volume of the fluid contained in the tank that is represented by the fill ratio, i.e., fluid
 137 height over total tank height. To account for this effect, three characteristic fill ratios are
 138 considered, resulting to the development of three distinct tank models per tank type: an almost

139 full tank with 90% fill ratio, a roughly half-full tank with 60% fill ratio, and a nearly empty
 140 tank with 30% fill ratio. The surrogate numerical model developed by Bakalis et al. [18] is
 141 adopted here to assess the seismic performance of the liquid storage tanks. The Bakalis et al.
 142 [18] tank model is employed for the tanks under investigation, assuming that the latter are
 143 unanchored (resting on a concrete foundation) and have a fixed roof. The tank model consists
 144 of a single mass, which is representative of the impulsive fluid mass, connected to an elastic
 145 beam-column element; the latter is supported by a set of radial rigid-beam spokes, each resting
 146 on multilinear elastic edge springs to account for uplifting. Three critical failure modes are
 147 considered in the model, namely roof and upper shell damage due to sloshing, excessive base
 148 plate rotation, and elephant's foot buckling of the lower shell course. Only sliding is not
 149 accounted for. The vibration periods of the impulsive and convective masses of the tanks are
 150 listed in Table 3. As a final remark about the tanks, it is acknowledged that, in many cases,
 151 volatile liquids are stored in tanks with a floating roof. Still, the tanks of the examined HDS
 152 unit are fixed-roof ones.

153 Table 2. Liquid storage tanks of the HDS unit and their salient characteristics [ρ_f : product density, H_t :
 154 tank height, R : tank radius, t_b : base plate thickness, t_a : annular ring thickness, t_w : equivalent wall
 155 thickness, f_y : steel yield strength].

ID	Product	ρ_f (kg/m ³)	H_t (m)	R (m)	t_b (mm)	t_a (mm)	t_w (mm)	f_y (MPa)
TK-01/02	Naphtha	750	22.0	42.7	6.4	11.0	33.2	235
TK-03	Gasoline	750	22.0	42.7	6.4	11.0	33.2	235
TK-04	Gasoil (Diesel)	845	22.0	42.7	6.4	11.0	33.2	235

156
 157 Table 3. Vibration periods of fluid components of tanks with different fill ratios [T_i : impulsive vibration
 158 period, T_c : convective vibration period].

ID	Fill ratio (%)	T_i (s)	T_c (s)
TK-01/02	90	0.35	15.02
	60	0.24	13.26
	30	0.11	11.50
TK-03	90	0.35	15.02
	60	0.24	13.26
	30	0.11	11.50
TK-04	90	0.37	15.02
	60	0.26	13.26
	30	0.12	11.50

159
 160 **3.2 Pumps**

161 The pumps of the examined HDS unit are all located on the ground level, which is typical
 162 practice in refineries. Pumps are a critical part of the refinery units as they ensure the smooth
 163 and sufficient (i.e., in correct pressure and flow volume) circulation of fluids in the extensive
 164 piping network. Pumps are modelled as single degree of freedom (SDOF) systems and are
 165 considered to be anchored to a solid concrete foundation. Each pump weights 500kg. A
 166 damping ratio of 2% is adopted based on the suggested values by Kazantzi et al. [22]. The
 167 fundamental periods of all the pumps are assumed to be equal to 0.10s in both x and y

168 directions, due to the strong fixed conditions of the machinery on its foundation for operational
169 reasons (vibration). A Peak Component Acceleration (PCA) demand is computed by
170 calculating the ground spectral acceleration, based on the acceleration input (i.e., recorded
171 ground motion), evaluated at each pump fundamental period in both the global x and y
172 directions. The earthquake-resistant design of the anchorage has been performed based on the
173 provisions of EN 1998-1:2004 [32]. This essentially implies that overstrength, rather than
174 ductility, is the main seismic resistance mechanism, practically ensuring an elastic response,
175 which is also required for operational reasons.

176 3.3 Equipment-supporting building and heat exchangers

177 The heat exchangers in the HDS unit are nested within a two-storey equipment-supporting
178 building. The building is a two-storey reinforced concrete moment-resisting open-frame
179 structure. Excluding the area of cantilevers, the building has floor dimensions of 15.2×8.2 m
180 with a story height of 5.5m. Heat exchanger E-01 is located at the ground level, while heat
181 exchangers E-02A and E-02B are located on the first floor, and heat exchangers E-03A and E-
182 03B at the second floor. Each heat exchanger weights 10,000kg. The total mass of the building
183 including the nested heat exchangers, other than E-01 on the ground level, is 611,500kg. The
184 equipment-supporting building is considered fixed to the ground and it is depicted in Figure 2.
185 Equipment-supporting industrial buildings are typically of high-strength low-ductility design
186 for non-seismic related reasons, such as operational integrity and fireproofing [22]; therefore,
187 all structural elements of the building are modelled as elastic beam-column elements. The slab
188 at each floor level is modelled as a rigid diaphragm, which implies that the floor slabs are thick
189 enough to provide sufficient in-plane rigidity. Rayleigh damping is employed and in particular
190 a damping ratio of 5% is assigned to the first and second global translational modes of
191 vibration. The first and second modes of vibration of the building, which are 0.21s and 0.20s
192 along the x and y directions, respectively, are shown in Figure 3. The interested reader may
193 find more details about the modelling background in the work of Kazantzi et al. [22].

194

195

196 Figure 2. 3D representation of the two-storey equipment-supporting building with its nested heat
197 exchangers shown in blue.

198 Figure 3. Vibration modes of the equipment-supporting building: (a) Mode 1 and (b) Mode 2 [the dotted
199 lines represent the undeformed shape, and the solid lines represent the deformed shape].

200 Heat exchangers on the first and second floor are anchored to the building slab. They are not
201 incorporated explicitly in the building model; instead, the cascade modelling approach is
202 employed, introducing them as point masses in the overall model. This is because their mass
203 of 10,000kg each is significantly lower than the structure's mass; therefore, the effect of
204 dynamic interaction between the structure and components is insignificant (e.g., [33]). For
205 computing heat exchanger response, we use the acceleration time histories at the anchor points
206 of heat exchangers located on floor levels other than the ground. Based on the acceleration
207 input and the estimated period of the heat exchangers in each principal direction, a PCA demand
208 is computed by calculating the corresponding floor spectral acceleration. A damping ratio of
209 2% is adopted for all heat exchangers. The fundamental periods of all heat exchangers are
210 assumed equal to 0.15s and 0.40s in the global x and y directions, respectively. For the heat
211 exchanger located at the ground level, which is anchored to the building foundation, PCA
212 demand is identical to the ground spectral acceleration evaluated at the component period in
213 the x and y directions, in the same manner as for the pumps. An elastic anchorage system
214 designed as per EN 1998-1:2004 [32] is assumed for the heat exchangers.

215 3.4 Furnace

216 The furnace in the HDS unit heats the process fluid to the optimal temperature required for the
217 removal of sulphur compounds in the reactors. The compartments of a typical industrial
218 furnace, starting from the lower to the higher level, are the firebox, the radiant section, the
219 convection section, and the stack. In the firebox, which is located at the bottom of the radiant
220 section, burners are placed on the floor or the walls of the shell and produce heat by
221 combustion. The process fluid inside the furnace circulates in tubes. The fluid enters the furnace
222 near the stack (i.e., on the upper part of the shell) and exits the furnace near the bottom, close
223 to the burners. The area closer to the stack is called the convection section because in this area
224 heat transfer is performed primarily through convection, while in the lower area of the shell,
225 heat transfer is primarily performed through radiation, hence the name of the radiant section.
226 The firebox is usually lined internally with a refractory layer, a brick lining specially designed
227 to withstand and reflect heat, while the convection and radiant sections are usually lined with
228 special insulation and refractory materials [34]. Combustion gases that are generated for heat
229 production rise to the stack and are released into the atmosphere.

230 The examined furnace, being illustrated in Figure 4(a), is a typical cabin furnace used in the
231 petrochemical industry (e.g., [35]). The dimensions of the furnace are listed in Table 4, where
232 width coincides with x axis and length with y axis. The furnace has a total mass of 19,107kg

233 and is made of S275R steel grade with a mean yield stress of 397.56MPa [36]. The reduced-
 234 order numerical model for the analysis of the furnace is based on the lumped mass model shown
 235 in Figure 4(b) and the guidelines of Karaferis et al. [21]. The developed numerical model
 236 consists of concentrated masses attached to elastic beam-column elements. A total of 22
 237 concentrated masses are included. The masses considered represent the self-weight of each
 238 segment (i.e., radiant section, convection section, stack transition, stack), also accounting for
 239 the firebricks at the bottom of the furnace, the ceramic fibre lining, and internal piping. P- Δ
 240 effects are accounted for in the structural analysis. The furnace is anchored (fixed) directly on
 241 its concrete mat foundation. It should be noted that in some cases, industrial furnaces are placed
 242 on reinforced concrete short columns that can modify the dynamic behaviour due to the
 243 presence of weak shear elements. If that were the case, an update of the numerical model would
 244 be needed. A damping ratio is set at 2% for both the first and third translation modes of
 245 vibration. The modal analysis yielded the fundamental translational period of vibration of the
 246 furnace of 0.12s in the global x direction and 0.11s in the global y direction, with the third mode
 247 having a period of 0.03s. Given the adoption of a lumped mass model attached to beam-column
 248 elements, no vibration modes are displayed for the furnace. It is noted that non-structural
 249 elements, such as internal piping or fibre lining, are not included in the model itself. Instead,
 250 the integrity of these elements is indirectly evaluated through appropriate damage states [24].

251

Table 4. Dimensions of the furnace.

Furnace section	Parameter	Value
Stack	Diameter (m)	0.84
	Height (m)	9.35
	Shell thickness (mm)	6.35
Stack transition	Width (m)	0.94
	Length (m)	3.30-0.97
	Height (m)	1.63
	Shell thickness (mm)	6.35
Convection section	Width (m)	1.12
	Length (m)	6.50
	Height (m)	2.27
Radiant section	Shell thickness (mm)	6.35
	Width (m)	2.28
	Length (m)	6.50
	Height (m)	4.13
	Shell thickness (mm)	6.35

252

253

254 Figure 4. (a) 3D representation of the furnace; (b) Generic representation of the lumped mass numerical
 255 model used for the assessment of the furnace and steel process towers.

256 3.5 Reactors and Stripper

257 The reactors and the stripper are both steel process towers. Reactors in the HDS unit facilitate
 258 chemical reactions under controlled pressure and temperature to remove sulphur compounds
 259 from the process fluid. The stripper, on the other hand, separates light hydrocarbons and other
 260 volatile components from the process fluid using steam to ensure the final product meets purity
 261 specifications. The towers are 32.73m high, with an internal diameter equal to 2.6m. The shell
 262 thickness of the towers varies along the height of the structures, resulting in four courses with
 263 wall thicknesses equal to 16mm (from 0.00 to 14.85m), 18mm (from 14.85 to 23.65m), 19mm
 264 (from 23.65 to 26.83mm), and 18mm (from 26.83 to 32.73m) from base to top. The towers are
 265 constructed from S275 grade steel with mean yield strength of 380MPa. The total mass of each
 266 tower is 49,000kg. The reactors and the stripper are anchored (fixed) on their concrete mat
 267 foundation. As in [9, 21], the base anchorage and skirt support of all the towers are assumed
 268 to be sufficiently oversized as per standard practice. Therefore, they are assumed not to be
 269 vulnerable to seismic action; consequently, uplift, overturning, sliding, or deformations of the
 270 skirt shell are not considered in the simplified model. The lumped mass numerical model shown
 271 in Figure 4(b) is adopted for the analysis of the process towers. The model consists of 16
 272 concentrated masses connected to elastic beam-column elements. The assigned masses are
 273 representative of the structure's self-weight, which varies with varying thickness of different
 274 courses along the height of the structure. The stiffness of the beam-column elements is
 275 calibrated to represent the stiffness of each tower course. P- Δ effects are accounted for in the
 276 structural analysis. A damping ratio of 2% is adopted for the first and third vibration modes.
 277 The modal analysis yielded the first and second translational periods of vibration of 0.49s, with
 278 a third translational mode of 0.08s. More details on the modelling background can be found in
 279 Karaferis et al. [21].

280 3.6 High-temperature Separator

281 The high-temperature separator is a horizontal vessel that weighs 10,000kg and is located at
 282 the ground level. It separates the hydrogen sulphide from the hydrocarbon liquid after the
 283 reactor, ensuring efficient recycling of hydrogen and preparing the liquid for further processing.
 284 The high-temperature separator, similarly to the pumps and the E-01 heat exchanger, is
 285 anchored to the ground via an elastic anchorage system designed as per EN 1998-1:2004 [31].
 286 The separator is modelled as an SDOF system. A damping ratio of 2% is adopted for the
 287 separator, with its fundamental periods assumed to be equal to 0.15s and 0.40s in the x and y
 288 directions, respectively, based on the values suggested by Kazantzi et al. [22]. The PCA demand
 289 is computed by calculating the ground spectral acceleration evaluated at each fundamental
 290 period in both the global x and y directions.

291 3.7 Piping

292 The piping network considered for the HDS unit includes pipes of 6", 10", 12", and 24" (inch)
 293 diameter in straight segments, elbows, and tees. The piping network within the HDS unit is
 294 above ground without any pipe racks in the unit. Pipe racks are versatile open-frame steel
 295 structures that are typically encountered in oil refineries for supporting piping (see, for
 296 example, [37]). The refinery unit at hand does not include any pipe racks due to its
 297 configuration and arranging of its components/assets. The developed model of the unit includes
 298 the main piping that connects the units' main components/assets, while secondary piping has
 299 been excluded from the analysis for simplicity reasons. All pipelines are made of API5L-X65
 300 steel grade with a mean yield stress of 448.5MPa. The geometric characteristics of the pipes
 301 are shown in Table 5. The diameter-to-thickness ratio (d_m/t) is also listed in Table 5 because
 302 it determines the slenderness of the pipe and, consequently, characterises its structural response.

303 Table 5. Geometric characteristics of selected pipes for HDS unit [d_{out} : pipe outside diameter, d_{in} : pipe
 304 internal diameter, t : pipe wall thickness, d_m : pipe mean diameter].

Parameter / Pipe diameter (in)	6"	10"	12"	24"
d_{out} (mm)	168	273	324	610
d_{in} (mm)	146	248	299	584
t (mm)	11.0	12.5	12.5	13.0
d_m (mm)	157	261	312	597
d_m/t	14.3	20.5	24.5	46.3

305

306 Elbows, tee junctions, and nozzles (collectively referred to as fittings) were identified as critical
 307 locations in the piping network due to their increased flexibility compared to straight pipes and
 308 the possible intensification of stresses due to their geometric irregularity [11,19]. Typically,
 309 fittings are modelled with shell elements to account for the cross-section ovalisation, local
 310 buckling occurrence, and the effect of internal pressure. However, this modelling approach
 311 requires results from experimental testing for calibration and may add significant
 312 computational cost, particularly for large and/or complex models (e.g., [11, 38-42]).

313 Particularly for elbows, to overcome the aforementioned limitations, researchers, such as Bursi
 314 et al. [19], have accounted for the increment in flexibility by defining an equivalent straight

315 beam element adjusted to the relevant curved elbow according to EN 13480-3:2017 [43].
 316 Paolacci et al. [40] have carried out a comparative study and showed that there is sufficient
 317 convergence between the numerical results obtained from detailed models compared to those
 318 from the modified beam elements. To that effect, the latter approach was adopted hereinafter
 319 for modelling elbows.

320 The length of the equivalent straight beam element L is equal to two times the mean diameter
 321 of the pipe (d_m), following the findings of Bursi et al. [19]. The effect of flexibility of an elbow
 322 spreads across this length L . An overview of the adopted equivalent straight elbow is offered
 323 in Figure 5.

324

325 Figure 5. Equivalent straight elbow (adapted from Bursi et al. [19]).

326 For defining an equivalent straight beam element, an equivalent inertia modulus [19] is
 327 estimated as:

$$J^* = \frac{\sqrt{2}J(2d_{out} + R)}{4d_{out} + Rk_B} \quad (1)$$

328 where k_B is the flexibility factor, defined as the flexibility of an elbow divided by the flexibility
 329 of a straight pipe with the same dimensions, J is the inertia modulus of the circular piping
 330 section, d_{out} is the elbow outside diameter, and R is the elbow radius. Then, k_B can be
 331 calculated after ASME B31.3 [44] as:

$$k_B = \frac{1.65}{h} \quad (2)$$

332 where h is the flexibility characteristic:

$$h = \frac{4Rt}{d_m^2} \quad (3)$$

333 while t is the elbow wall thickness and d_m is the elbow mean diameter.

334 Then, the thickness of the equivalent straight elbow, t_{eq} , is calculated from the equivalent
 335 inertia modulus as follows:

$$J^* = \frac{\pi}{64} (d_{out}^4 - (d_{out}^4 - 2t_{eq})) \quad (4)$$

336 It should be noted that the calculation of the parameter k_B after ASME B31.3 leads to over-
 337 conservative results [19, 20, 45], a condition that is not desirable for an unbiased assessment
 338 of a piping network. Because of this, several researchers (e.g., [19, 45-47]) have developed

339 numerical models to obtain more realistic flexibility estimates to represent pipe elbows. Figure
 340 6(a) provides examples of these results. This figure illustrates the relationship between k_B and
 341 h derived from ASME B31.3, plotted against numerical data from Thomas [45] using the finite
 342 difference method, from Martinez et al. [46] using the boundary element method, and from
 343 Bursi et al. [19] using the finite element method.

344 Figure 6. (a) Flexibility factor k_B as a function of flexibility characteristic h for pipes of varying
 345 geometries (i.e., diameter and thickness) using alternative approaches; (b) Flexibility factors k_B for
 346 pipes of varying geometries, showing the expressions fitted to Martinez et al. [46], and Thomas [45]
 347 against the respective data.

348 It is observed in Figure 6(a) that the equation given in ASME B31.3 yields larger k_B values for
 349 pipes of any given flexibility characteristic h , while numerical data produced by Thomas [45],
 350 Martinez et al. [46], and Bursi et al. [19] show lower k_B values for the respective pipe
 351 geometries analysed.

352 Based on the data in Figure 6(a), we adopted the following k_B values for our analysis:

- 353 • For h values lower than 0.2, the data from Thomas [45] were used because they were the
 354 only data points available for this range of h . Numerical simulations by Thomas [45]
 355 showed that the attached pipe provides a decrease in flexibility of 14.5% compared to the
 356 flexibility specified in ASME B31.3, and therefore:

$$k_{B,Thomas} = \frac{1.41}{h} \quad (5)$$

- 357 • For h values greater than or equal to 0.2, the data from Martinez et al. [46] were used
 358 because they follow a trend similar to that of the ASME B31.3 and the numerical data
 359 produced by Thomas [45] but are also closer to numerical data from Bursi et al. [19]. For
 360 using the data, we decided to develop a regression model, as plotted in Figure 6(b). The
 361 regression equation based on the data from Martinez et al. [46] is:

$$k_{B,Martinez} = \frac{1.01}{h} \quad (6)$$

362 Note that for more detailed applications, one should ideally develop case-specific numerical
 363 models to obtain the values of parameter k_B for the fittings at hand. Nevertheless, the simpler
 364 approach adopted fits better our need to efficiently model a refinery unit and offer a scalable
 365 methodology that can cover the entire facility as needed. The parameters of the equivalent
 366 elbows for the piping network of the HDS unit are tabulated in Table 6.

367 Table 6. Parameters for equivalent elbows [d_{out} : pipe outside diameter, d_{in} : pipe internal diameter, t :
368 pipe wall thickness, d_m : pipe mean diameter, R : elbow radius, h : elbow flexibility characteristic, k_B :
369 elbow flexibility factor, J : pipe inertia modulus, J^* : inertia modulus of equivalent straight pipe, t_{eq} : wall
370 thickness of the equivalent straight pipe].

Parameter / Pipe diameter (in)	6"	10"	12"	24"
d_{out} (mm)	168	273	324	610
d_{in} (mm)	146	248	299	584
t (mm)	11.0	12.5	12.5	13.0
d_m (mm)	157	261	312	597
d_m/t	14.3	20.5	24.5	46.3
R (mm)	252	410	486	915
h	0.45	0.30	0.25	0.13
k_B (Adopted)	2.25	3.35	4.03	10.56
k_B (ASME B31.3)	3.67	5.47	6.59	12.36
J (mm ⁴)	1.68E+07	8.70E+07	1.49E+08	1.09E+09
J^* (mm ⁴)	1.13E+07	4.77E+07	7.32E+07	2.71E+08
t_{eq} (mm)	6.9	6.4	5.8	3.1
d_{out} , elbow (mm)	168	273	324	610
d_{in} , elbow (mm)	161	267	318	607

371

372 Tee junctions and nozzles have also been identified as critical locations that may compromise
373 the integrity of piping systems. Detailed numerical models using shell elements have been
374 developed by researchers to represent the experimental behaviour of tee junctions and nozzles
375 (e.g., [11]). Nevertheless, research involving simplified or equivalent beam elements for
376 fittings has been focused mostly on elbows and is relatively scarce for tee junctions and nozzles.
377 ASME B31.3, for example, recommends a flexibility factor k_B equal to 1.0 for tee junctions,
378 and does not give any recommendation for nozzles. Because of this scarcity of data, the elbow
379 parameters in Table 6 have also been adopted for tees and nozzles.

380 Specifically, for tees, we assume a distance $L = 2d_m$ from the tee intersection point for
381 stiffness reduction, with d_m being the mean diameter of the pipe, as shown in Figure 7(a). This
382 distance L is the same that Bursi et al. [19] adopted to account for the spreading of flexibility
383 from an elbow into the connected straight pipe. For nozzles, the same distance L for the stiffness
384 reduction is assumed, with distance L being measured from the intersection of the piping with
385 each component, as shown in Figure 7(b). It is noted that this length L is adopted due to a lack
386 of data in the literature. Again, a more detailed application should include customised
387 numerical models for obtaining a more accurate representation of L and k_B , but this refinement
388 is out of the scope of our study.

389 Figure 7. (a) Distance for stiffness reduction in tees; (b) Distance for stiffness reduction in nozzles; (c)
 390 Pipe resting on concrete sleeper.

391 Regarding supports, the piping in consideration rests on concrete bases, so-called “sleepers”,
 392 as depicted in Figure 7(c). Sleepers are placed every 5m in straight segments and additionally
 393 at locations where elbows or tees are present, as per industry practice. Sleepers provide full
 394 restraint in the vertical direction, no restraint in the longitudinal direction, and partial restraint
 395 in the transverse direction. A maximum allowable lateral displacement equal to 50% of the
 396 pipe outer diameter is assumed in the transverse direction following typical construction
 397 practice in order to allow small transverse displacement due to thermal expansion. To model
 398 this behaviour, we employed the so-called “gap” material available in the OpenSees library to
 399 introduce a zero-length composite transverse spring connecting the pipe to the sleeper that
 400 allows a zero-stiffness translation in both tension and compression response before engaging a
 401 stiff resistance.

402 To preserve the interaction of piping with the connected assets, such as liquid storage tanks,
 403 the dynamic characteristics of said assets should be introduced in the piping network model.
 404 The model of the equipment-supporting building is incorporated in its full extent, to ensure
 405 capturing the differential displacement of pipes connecting equipment at different floors.
 406 Ideally, this would also be done for all assets, leading to a comprehensive piping-and-asset
 407 HDS unit model. Given that little information is available about the piping connections to these
 408 assets and to lighten the computational load, all non-building assets are replaced by a two-
 409 degree-of-freedom single-mass approximation. Specifically, concentrated masses are
 410 introduced at the interconnection locations, with translational mass values that match the total
 411 asset mass. Elastic translational zero-length springs are attached to said masses in each global
 412 direction (x and y). They are calibrated so that the period in each direction coincides with the
 413 respective fundamental period of the corresponding asset. Thus, they preserve the fundamental
 414 modes of the assets, only missing some higher mode effects. Note that, per the employed

415 approximation, all piping is assumed to be connected to the asset at the effective first-mode
416 height. In reality, different pipes may be connected at different heights, requiring some detailed
417 information (that is not always available) and a somewhat more complex model to account for
418 the dependence of deformation response on the attachment height. For simplicity, we opted for
419 the height-independent approach. It is noted that, as the piping system model depends on the
420 translational mass and fundamental period of each interconnected asset (e.g., tanks or reactors),
421 it also depends on the liquid storage tanks fill ratio that defines the vibrating mass of the
422 tank. Following a sensitivity analysis, it was found that the structural response of the piping
423 model is not significantly affected by variations in tank fill ratios. Therefore, it was decided to
424 select a set of predefined characteristic fill ratios for the tanks, namely TK-01, TK-02, and TK-
425 04 with a 60% fill ratio and TK-03 with 90% fill ratio to represent the typical operational
426 condition of the HDS unit. It is noted that the effect of the pipe on each single asset is not
427 considered, but, contrarily, the effect of each single asset on the pipe system is taken into
428 account. In other words, aspects such as pipe-to-tank connections (e.g., nozzles) and integrity
429 of piping mechanical components (e.g., valves) are not examined because their impact on the
430 seismic risk is nontrivial and requires detailed further investigation.

431 Straight piping segments are modelled with elastic beam elements, while elbows, tees, and
432 nozzles are modelled with distributed-plasticity elements based on the force formulation. The
433 Ramberg-Osgood [48] stress-strain relationship is adopted to account for the material
434 nonlinearity in elbows, tees, and nozzles. The material parameters for API5L-X65 steel grade
435 are adopted from Kouretzis et al. [49]. P- Δ effects are accounted for the entire piping model.

436 The piping network connecting all internal components of the HDS unit is depicted in Figure
437 8, and the full piping network, including the liquid storage tanks, is depicted in Figure 9. In
438 both figures assets are represented by dots and piping segments are represented by straight
439 lines. The damping ratio for all piping elements is set equal to 0.5% in the first and second
440 modes of vibration based on the suggestions from Bursi et al. [19]. The fundamental period of
441 vibration of the piping system is equal to 8.7s, while the second and third periods of vibration
442 are 7.4s and 6.4s, respectively. The vibration modes of the piping system are displayed in
443 Figure 10. Given that different parts of the piping system are excited in different vibration
444 modes, the first 6 vibration modes of the system are plotted to offer an overview of the piping
445 response. Also, to showcase these different parts of the piping system, the full system for modes
446 1 to 3 [Figure 10(a) to Figure 10(c)] and only the central part of the system for modes 4 to 6
447 [Figure 10(d) to Figure 10(f)] are plotted.

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Figure 8. Piping network connecting components of the HDS unit.

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Figure 9. Piping network connecting assets of the HDS unit, appearing in detail in Figure 8, with the four liquid storage tanks.

454 Figure 10. Vibration modes of the piping system: (a) Mode 1; (b) Mode 2; (c) Mode 3; (d) Mode 4; (e)
 455 Mode 5; (f) Mode 6. Plots (a) to (c) show the entire piping system, and plots (d) to (f) show the central
 456 part of the piping system. The dotted lines correspond to the undeformed shape, while the solid ones to
 457 the deformed shape.

458 4 Conclusions

459 The make-up, operation, and modelling of the critical assets in a hydrodesulphurisation unit of
 460 a typical crude oil refinery were presented: liquid storage tanks, pumps, heat exchangers, an
 461 equipment-supporting building, a furnace, reactors, a high temperature separator, a stripper,
 462 and the connecting piping network. Reduced-order numerical models were developed for the
 463 unit assets, while an available surrogate model for the liquid storage tanks was adopted from

464 the literature. In order to account for the operational and (partial) structural interconnection of
465 the assets via piping, a novel reduced-order model of the piping network was developed
466 considering in detail its critical parts, namely tees and elbows (fittings), together with the
467 salient dynamic characteristics of the assets. Modelling this dynamic interaction of assets and
468 piping is critical for the piping, but also for the functionality of the unit, as even a single pipe
469 failure can have significant operational and safety consequences. Therefore, including such
470 interactions in the piping model is essential to offer high-fidelity risk estimates. The reduced-
471 order models typically offer a simplified representation of the actual assets. Still, they do
472 capture the main functional and structural failure modes necessary for seismic fragility and risk
473 assessments. Far from typical building-stock urban or regional exposure studies, the ensemble
474 of these assets is much more than just a sum of the respective parts. This is a cohesive
475 production unit, whose operation depends on the individual assets in a complex way, allowing
476 for redundancies in some cases (e.g., pumps and reactors), but not in others (e.g., stripper,
477 separator, furnace). The developed exposure model and the numerical models of the
478 interconnected assets presented are then employed for the seismic damage assessment of the
479 refinery critical unit in the companion paper [24].

480

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492 The authors declare no potential conflicting interests concerning the research, authorship,
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